

Quality of Life in Oncology Measuring What Matters for Cancer Patients and Survivors in Europe: The EUonQoL Project

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Abstract: Cancer, in Europe, is the second cause of death. In addition, there is an unacceptable variability in terms of access to innovation, quality of care, and outcomes, within and between countries. The European Union has activated an unprecedented initiative to fight cancer by launching Europe's Beating Cancer Plan and the Cancer Mission. The goals are to reduce mortality, increase survival, and ameliorate quality of life by increasing knowledge, improving quality of care, and reducing inequalities through interventions on actionable determinants of variability. A competitive call was launched with the objective to develop and validate a set of quality of life and patient preference measures for cancer patients and survivors, to be used for routine data collection all over Europe. A consortium, the EUonQoL, was funded, including partners from 41 countries with 55 participants. It will start the activities on January 2023 and results are expected by December 2024. **Key words:** *European Union, inequalities, quality of care, quality of life, quality of life assessment*

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CANCER, IN EUROPE, is the second cause of death and the first of suffering for patients and caregivers, as well as having an enormous impact on health systems and families in economic terms. In addition to the impressive current and expected epidemiological data—2.7 million new cases and 1.3 million deaths in 2020, expected to increase of about 25% by 2035—there is an unacceptable variability in terms of access to innovation, quality of care, and outcomes, within and between countries in Europe. This variability is due to several factors, including the amount of gross national product allocated by each member state to health care—ranging from 5.4% to 11.2%—and the difference in purchasing power, as part of health care expenditures is covered by voluntary out-of-pocket money (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2022).

The European Union (EU) has activated an unprecedented initiative to fight cancer by launching Europe's Beating Cancer Plan and the Cancer Mission. The European Commission has earmarked a total of €4 billion, including €1.25 billion from the EU4Health

Programme. An additional financial support will be available through the Digital Europe Programme and the Horizon Europe, which could provide a total of up to €2 billion to support the Mission of Cancer and other cancer-related research projects (European-Canadian Cancer Network, 2022). Several competitive calls, some already available and other expected in the next year, will be published.

The goals of Europe's Beating Cancer Plan and the Cancer Mission are to reduce mortality, increase survival, and ameliorate QoL by increasing knowledge, improving quality of care, and reducing inequalities through the limitation of unacceptable, yet actionable, determinants of variability.

In the context of the first phase, the call HORIZON-MISS-2021-CANCER-02-02, launched in December 2021, had the objective to develop and validate a set of quality of life and patient preference measures for cancer patients and survivors, to be used for routine data collection all over Europe. This call is an opportunity to add patient perspectives within multiomics personalized oncology, an important new step in the progress toward patient-centered care.

Quality of life (QoL) is an elusive term that can have different interpretations depending on the context (Apolone, 1998; Haraldstad et al., 2019). The social sciences interpret QoL as satisfaction and happiness measured as the achievement of aspirations and/or the realization of individual expectations. In this definition, the perception that an individual has of one's health is only one of the many possible concepts/determinants of QoL. Health itself is now conceived not only as the absence of disease and disability, but also as a presence of physical, mental, and social well-being and functioning that may be modulated/modified by all of those factors capable of intervening on this perception, including health care interventions. In the health care setting, a definition of health-related QoL (HR-QoL) has been proposed to narrow the field of interest and subsequent evaluations. Many tools, generic or disease and treatment specific, either static or dynamic/adaptative, have been proposed to be

used in clinical trials, clinical practice, and to monitor the yield of health care interventions on the general population.

Recently, to better define these concepts from an operational point of view, the terms PROMs and PREMs have been introduced (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services FDA, 2006). PROMs (patient-reported outcome measures) have been defined as any report of the status of a patient's health condition that comes directly from the patient, without interpretation of the patient's response by a clinician or anyone else. PREMs (patient-reported experience measures) are self-reported questionnaires assessing overall patient experience while receiving health care, including satisfaction. In contrast to PROMs, PREMs do not focus on outcomes of care but on the impact the process of the care has on factors like communication and timeliness of assistance.

The improvement or preservation of QoL is 1 of the 3 pillars of the Mission on Cancer (Research and Innovation, 2022), which underpins the needs of patients from cancer diagnosis across treatment, survivorship, and advanced terminal stages of noncurable cases. The burden of cancer and cancer treatment on QoL is well recognized, while clinical trials and real-world data show the positive effects of routine PROM assessment on patient well-being and use of health care resources. Nonetheless, full implementation of HR-QoL assessment in routine oncology practice is not yet part of standard of care. In the same way, health care systems and cancer control programs do not take into consideration QoL measures when devising clinical, societal, and healthcare policymaking systems.

In order to apply to the HORIZON-MISS-2021-CANCER-02-02 competitive call, we constituted the EUonQoL consortium including partners from the 27 EU member states and 4 associated countries, for a total number of 55 participants. The EUonQoL consortium brings together the most knowledgeable expertise in the field of quality-of-life research, cancer patients' organizations, administrators, policy makers, and comprehensive cancer centers in Europe. OEI, the

Figure 1. European countries involved in the pilot validation study.

Organisation of European Cancer Institutes (OECI, <https://www.oeci.eu/>) including more than 123 cancer Centers, is also involved and will contribute to the coordination of the pilot validation study recruiting 4000 cancer patients in Europe (Figure 1). This wide collaboration had the overall goal to be instrumental to the progress of the Mission on Cancer Plan, through the development, validation, and exploitation of the European Oncology Quality of Life toolkit (EUonQoL-Kit) among European cancer patients and survivors.

Plenty of generic and either disease- or treatment-specific questionnaires have been developed and validated to measure QoL of patients with cancer, mainly being used in the cancer research context. However, most QoL instruments have been developed a few decades ago, by researchers to meet their own information needs and designed to be filled in by paper and pencil. The EUonQoL project aims to review existing scales and to develop new metrics overcoming the limitations of previous tools. The EUonQoL will be a new digital system for QoL self-assessment, available in several European languages and developed from the patient perspective. In fact, the overall project is based on participatory codesign research principles, through the involvement of a rep-

resentative panel of stakeholders, including patients and their caregivers throughout all project phases (Figure 2). More specifically the EUonQoL aims at:

- identifying gaps in the body of evidence and in currently available QoL assessment tools;
- developing the EUonQoL-Kit, an innovative, unified system for QoL assessment for cancer patients in different disease stages of their disease trajectory: those receiving treatment, survivors, and in need of palliative care;
- translating and culturally adapting the EUonQoL-Kit in all the 27 European countries' languages;
- validating the EUonQoL-Kit in a pilot survey of 4000 cancer patients and survivors enrolled in a cooperative network of cancer centers covering the 27 EU member states;
- identifying individual and country-specific factors associated to QoL in Europe; and
- developing procedures and actions aimed at establishing the basis for future monitoring of QoL in European cancer patients and survivors using the EUonQoL-Kit.

The EUonQoL project, coordinated by the Italian National Cancer Institute in Milan, was funded and will start the activities in January

Figure 2. Project aims.

2023. First results are expected by December 2024. In the first phase of the implementation of the Cancer Mission and Europe's Beating Cancer Plan, several research and policy projects have been approved and funded with the goal to increase transnational collaboration, including multiple stakeholders in the codesign and implementation. There are many obstacles and barriers, some related to organizational skills and others to financial competences. The EU has shown a great

willingness and a good attitude in trying to solve some of the problems that underlie the variability in quality and outcomes: the European oncology community has reacted sharply by forming large, multinational, and multistakeholder consortia with relevant projects. But now it is imperative that politicians and decision-makers of the individual states understand the great opportunity by favoring changes based on the results of the various projects.

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